

LARGE SCALE BUCKLING EXPERIMENT AND VALIDATION OF PREDICTIVE CAPABILITIES

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SUMMARY: A 9m long airfoil blade section, designed to fail in buckling, has been build and tested destructively in a four-point bending configuration. The purpose of the test was to verify capabilities for predicting buckling of an airfoil section subject to bending. First an analytical method to calculate the critical bifurcation-buckling load of a generally laminated cylindrical shell is presented. The analytical approach is intended for used in the early design phase as a quick estimate of the buckling strength of the design. And also it has been used in the present paper in a structural design optimization scheme presented at the end of the paper, where the critical buckling load is maximized. Secondly a finite element approach is adopted. The commercial finite element package MSC.Patran and MSC.Nastran is used. A set of Patran Command Language routines has been written to automate the very time consuming task of building a finite element model of a blade section. Both geometry and layup data is read directly from ASCII files, which are generated by an in-house developed software, BladeStructure. The data in the ASCII files are then translated to a finite element model of the blade section via the set of PCL routines. Results obtained with the analytical method and the finite element approach are presented and compared with the test data. Finally an example of a gradient based structural design optimization is presented. The critical buckling load is maximized using the orientation of the plies in the layup as design variables.

KEYWORDS: buckling experiment, cylindrical shell, design optimization.

INTRODUCTION

The wind turbine industry has experienced a rapid expansion the past 20 years, with growth rates of 20-30% p.a. The industry environment is highly technological competitive with a constant focus of lowering the total cost per. kilowatt of electricity produced, without jeopardising high quality demands. As the rotor, traditionally is the most expensive single component, it is always an aim to reduce the cost of the blades. Pushing the material utilisation to the limit is a necessity for light and cost effective blades. As a consequence of the minimum material design strategy the structures are becoming thin-walled and buckling problems must be addressed. Today's blades are high performance, hybrid material structures with lengths of up to 60 meters. As a minimum, full-scale testing is always performed on new prototype blades. However full-scale testing is expensive and setting up a good data acquisition system is difficult because the area to monitor is large. Therefore to be able to test the structural integrity of new design concepts with low costs and in a short time, a generic 9m-airfoil section mould has been build. Recently, a buckling test has been carried out to verify the predictive capabilities of available buckling calculation tools, using both analytical and numerical methods. The present paper presents the results of the investigation.

LARGE SCALE BUCKLING EXPERIMENT

Structural design

For this test purpose a generic airfoil section has been used. In the present case a NACA 63₄-421 (Ref. 1) with a cord width of 1.17m has been chosen. As with most structural designs for modern wind turbine blades the 9m section is a hybrid structure. Here both carbon- and glass fibre as well as birch- and balsa wood have been used. All materials are laid up dry in an upper and lower shell mould and subsequently infused with an epoxy resin. Finally the two shells and the webs are joined with an adhesive bonding. In order to preserve transparency to visually inspect the materials before, during and after testing no gelcoat was used. An overview of the material distribution in the blade section is showed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Structural overview of the NACA 63₄-421 airfoil section

Test set-up

A 4-point bending configuration was used to obtain a section with a constant moment loading. The test set-up is schematically presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Schematic representation of the test set-up.

The blade section was loaded by applying equal loads to the two loading clamps. Thus the 2m test-section in the middle will have a uniform moment distribution. And the buckling critical area will be the compressively loaded spar cap on the test-section. The load was steadily increased until the specimen failed in buckling. During the test, the spar cap was visually monitored with a high-speed digital video camera recording with a 1 second pre-trigger at 1000 frames pr. second. 17 Strain gauges was placed on the centre of the spar cap with a mutual distance of 80 mm, which was predicted to yield 6 gauges pr. full sine wave in the buckled shape. Data was sampled from the 17 gauges at a rate of 200 Hz to ensure that data would be available at the onset of buckling.

PREDICTIVE CAPABILITIES

Two different approaches for predicting the onset of buckling was used in the present study. As a quick and dirty tool intended for use in the initial design phase, an analytical method was set up. In order for the analytical method to be applied in the context of a later structural design optimization it was necessary for the method to account for full anisotropy. I.e. all terms in the laminate stiffness matrix should be included. The second approach used was analysing the section in the commercial finite element package MSC.Patran and MSC.Nastran

Analytical method

In solving the problem analytically, some simplification is necessary. From experience the most buckling critical area of a blade is the spar cap. Geometrically the spar cap is simplified to a simply supported cylindrical shell panel loaded in uniaxial compression as showed in Fig.

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Fig. 3: Simplified model for analytical solution of the buckling problem

The buckling problem has been solved via the principle of minimum potential energy and the Rayleigh-Ritz method following a method originally proposed by N. Jaunky Ref. 2. Approximation of the displacement field (The Ritz functions) has been made using Legendre polynomials and the strain displacement relations have been set up so three different shell theories can be accounted for. In short the method can be outlined as follows:

In the strain displacement relations defined in Eqn. 2 the so-called tracer coefficients, C_1 and C_2 are used to incorporate different shell theories. Thus if $C_1 = C_2 = 1$ the first approximation of the Sander-Koiter (Ref. 3, Ref. 4) shell theory is obtained. If $C_1 = 1$ and $C_2 = 0$ Love's (Ref. 5) is obtained and finally setting $C_1 = C_2 = 0$ the Donnell's (Ref. 6) shell theory is obtained. All theories include transverse normal shear deformation. In the Sander-Koiter shell theory both the contribution of the transverse shear force intensity to the equilibrium of forces in the circumferential direction, and the contributions of transverse and axial displacement in the twist terms are included. Donnell's and the Sander-Koiter shell theories have been shown to give results in close agreement with those obtained by the finite element code STAGS (Ref 1), which is a finite element program for general-purpose analysis of shell structures. In the presentation of the results only results obtained by the Sander-Koiter shell theory is presented, but for the examples computed here, no significant difference was observed using the different shell theories.

In solving the buckling problem the principle of minimum potential energy has been followed. This states that during buckling the elastic energy stored in the structure is equal to

the work done by external forces. I.e. in minimizing the total potential energy Eqn 1 the critical buckling load can be determined.

$$\pi = U - W_d \quad (1)$$

U is the elastic energy stored in the structure and W_d is the work done by external forces.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} & \varepsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + \frac{w_0}{R} \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 &= \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} & \kappa_y &= \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial y} \\ \kappa_x &= \frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial x} & \kappa_{xy} &= \frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial x} + \frac{C_2}{2R} \left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \right) \\ \kappa_{xy} &= \frac{\partial \phi_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \phi_y}{\partial x} + \frac{C_2}{2R} \left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \right) & \gamma_{yz}^0 &= \phi_y + \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} - C_1 \frac{v_0}{R} \\ \gamma_{xz}^0 &= \phi_x + \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} & & \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

From the strain displacement relation Eqn. 2 the expression for the elastic energy stored in the structure can be formulated as Eqn. 3.

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_A \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz}^0 \\ \gamma_{yz}^0 \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & 0 & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & 0 & 0 \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & 0 & 0 \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} & 0 & 0 \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} & 0 & 0 \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{44} & D_{45} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{45} & D_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xz}^0 \\ \gamma_{yz}^0 \end{Bmatrix} dA \quad (3)$$

It can be seen in Eqn. 3, that no restriction is made on symmetry of the layup as all stiffness terms in the laminate stiffness matrix has been included.

Likewise the expression for the work done by external forces is defined from the non-linear strain displacement relations Eqn. 4.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xNL} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right) \\ \varepsilon_{yNL} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{v_0}{R} \right)^2 \right) \\ \gamma_{xyNL} &= -\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} + \frac{w}{R} \right) - \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \frac{v_0}{R} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

From this the work done by external forces is computed as:

$$W_d = \int_A \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \\ v_0 \\ R \\ w \\ R \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} N_x & N_{xy} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N_{xy} & 0 \\ N_{xy} & N_y & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_x & 0 & -N_{xy} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -N_{xy} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -N_{xy} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -N_{xy} & 0 & N_y & 0 & -N_{xy} \\ -N_{xy} & -N_y & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & N_{xy} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} \\ v_0 \\ R \\ w \\ R \end{Bmatrix} dA \quad (5)$$

Using the Rayleigh Ritz method for minimizing Eqn. 1 a set of Ritz functions for approximating the displacement field needs to be defined. Here Legendre polynomials has been used because when transforming the problem from a physical xy -domain to a computational $\xi\eta$ -domain, significant computational savings can be achieved, as the integration of the Ritz functions (Eqn. 3 and 5) over the $\xi\eta$ -domain can be done analytically. The transformation is done using standard bilinear shape functions known from basic finite element theory (See e.g. Ref. 7). Eqn.3 is written as:

$$U = \int_A \mathbf{E}_p^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{E}_p dA \quad (6)$$

\mathbf{E}_p is a vector containing the strains defined in the physical domain. \mathbf{E}_p is now transformed to the computational domain by standard bilinear shape functions.

$$\mathbf{E}_p = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{E}_c \quad (7)$$

Now the displacement field is approximated by the Ritz function

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ v_0 \\ w_0 \\ \phi_x \\ \phi_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & V_i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & W_i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi_{xi} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \phi_{yi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} a_{1i} \\ a_{2i} \\ a_{3i} \\ a_{4i} \\ a_{5i} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where in Eqn. 8 the capital U_i represents the i^{th} term in an N term approximation of the Legendre polynomial approximating the displacement u . the terms a_{1-5i} are unknown coefficients to be determined. From this \mathbf{E}_c in Eqn. 7 can be written as:

$$\mathbf{E}_c = \mathbf{\Theta}_i \mathbf{q}_i \quad (9)$$

Where $\mathbf{\Theta}_i$ is a matrix containing the Ritz functions defined in the computational domain. And \mathbf{q}_i is a vector of coefficient to the Ritz functions, which is unknown and to be determined. Inserting Eqn. 9 into Eqn. 7 and then Eqn. 7 into Eqn. 6 and rearranging we arrive at:

$$\begin{aligned}
U &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{Ac} \mathbf{q}_i^T [\boldsymbol{\Theta}_i^T \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{T} \boldsymbol{\Theta}_j] \mathbf{q}_j |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \\
U &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}_i^T \left\{ \int_{Ac} \mathbf{k}_{ij} |\mathbf{J}| d\xi d\eta \right\} \mathbf{q}_j \\
U &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}_i^T \mathbf{K}_{ij} \mathbf{q}_j
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

For the sake of brevity the expression for the work done by external forces is not derived, but the steps involved are identical to the once presented for obtaining the expression for the elastic energy and W_d is found as:

$$W_d = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}_i^T \mathbf{K}_{gij} \mathbf{q}_j \tag{11}$$

Eqn. 1 can now be written as:

$$\pi = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \mathbf{q}_i^T (\mathbf{K}_{ij} - \lambda \mathbf{K}_{gij}) \mathbf{q}_j \tag{12}$$

Where λ is a factor for the critical load to be determined. Minimizing Eqn 12 with respect to \mathbf{q}_i correspond to solving the problem

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathbf{K}_{ij} - \lambda \mathbf{K}_{gij}) \mathbf{q}_i = 0 \tag{13}$$

Eqn. 13 is seen to be an eigenvalue problem and can be solved using any standard eigenvalue solver. The lowest eigenvalue corresponds to the critical buckling load and the corresponding eigenvector describes the buckled mode shape. This analytical buckling method has been implemented in Matlab, and has been found computationally very efficient as integration of the stiffness matrices in Eqn 10 and Eqn. 11 can be done analytically when using Legendre polynomials as the Ritz functions.

Finite element model

The task of building finite element models of blade sections manually is time consuming. Therefore a set of Patran Command Language (PCL) routines for cost effective finite element model generation have been written. This enables the user to make a change in layup or geometry in a matter of minutes instead of hours or days. All data regarding geometry and layup is defined in ASCII files, which are written using in-house developed software, BladeStructure. The set of PCL routines reads the ASCII output files from BladeStructure and generates the finite element model directly from the data present. For large blade sections with complex layup these input files can be several hundred lines long, making manual input a very time consuming task. The model was build using MSC.Nastran PCOMP/CQUAD4 elements, which are 4-node isoparametric quadrilateral elements with composite option. In the finite element model the full 9m of the test specimen has been modelled. A total of 27.000 elements have been used. The elements have been distributed using an iso mesher with 270 mesh seeds in the axial direction and 100 in the circumferencial direction. The computation time involved in solving problems of this size is reasonable on a standard PC. The load has been applied as a distributed shear load to the webs at both ends of the structure. Displacement of the nodes over the loading clamps (see Fig. 2) was constrained in the z-direction. First a linear buckling analysis was performed. Using the predicted linear buckling load a finite element analysis where geometrically non-linear effects were taken into account was performed. The load was increased in 12 steps with a convergence criteria on the error on the work done of 0.1%. In the present analysis convergence could be reached just up until the

point, where bifurcation-buckling load was predicted with a linear buckling analysis, without using an arc-length procedure. After the point of the bifurcation-buckling load it was found necessary to interpolate in both load and displacement in order to trace the equilibrium path. However the solution for the post-buckling region is not presented in this paper as the structure is failing due to material failure before the theoretical bifurcation-buckling load, where strains are increased rapidly with little increase in load.

RESULTS

All results are compared in terms of strains in the middle of the spar cap in the test region and in terms of the critical buckling load since these are the test data is available from the buckling experiment. As an overview, the results from the experiment, the analytical solution and the finite element calculation are compared in Table 1.

	Buckling load, F (Fig. 2) [kN]	Derivation from test result
Experimental result	24.2	
Analytical (Linear estimate)	30.2	25%
Finite element result	30.7	27%

Table 1 Comparison of ultimate buckling load - test results and predictions

Results obtained with the analytical solution agree well with the finite element results. However they predict 25% and 27% higher buckling load respectively than what was obtained during the test. It is well known that any real structure contains imperfections, which might reduce the ultimate strength. Therefore another geometrically non-linear finite element analysis was performed, this time taking an imperfection field into account. The geometric imperfection used is chosen as a small offset of the nodes corresponding to the buckled shape. The size of the offset corresponds to the manufacturing tolerance of the mould, which for this case is set to 0.2mm. This will give a picture of the imperfection sensitivity of the structure. In Fig. 4 the strains in the middle of the spar cap at the onset of buckling is plotted against the axial position. Note from Fig. 2 the test region is seen to be located between the coordinates 3.5m and 5.5m.

Fig. 4: Strains at the middle of the spar cap.

Summary and concluding remarks

Comparing the results from the test with the results obtained with the analytical method and the finite element method showed that there was a discrepancy of 25-27% between test results and predicted results, whereas the finite element method and the analytical method agreed very well. The discrepancy has been sought explained by the fact that every real life structure contains geometric imperfections, which will lower the ultimate strength of the structure. Thus a finite element analysis was made were the model contained an initial imperfection, which was an offset of the nodes corresponding to the first eigenmode. The size of the offset was a max of 0.2mm, corresponding to the production tolerances of the mould for the 9m section. From this analysis significantly better agreement between the strain results at the maximum test load was obtained. On this basis it is suggested that a linear buckling analysis will over predict the ultimate strength of the blade. How much the strength is over predicted depends on the, size of the imperfections present in the blade and the sensitivity of the structure with respect to the imperfections. The theoretical bifurcation-buckling load was never reached in the test, but the blade showed a buckling like response of large local displacements (And thereby also strains) with little increase in the load. A response normally seen for structures with imperfections when the load is close to the bifurcation-buckling load. In effect it is suggested that a bifurcation buckling analysis with a knockdown factor applied on the buckling load will give a good estimate on the ultimate strength of the blade. The value of the knockdown factor will depend on the size of the imperfections as well as the imperfection sensitivity. For the present design a factor of 1.25 can be used to assess the ultimate strength of the blade.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

In the following the layup of the spar cap is redesigned with the aim of optimizing the buckling load of the structure. Typically there is a design constraint on the global bending stiffness of the blade since fatigue issues often drive the design. Hence the max strain of the material is a constraining factor. Today's carbon fibre materials have excellent fatigue properties and thus the material is strained still harder to gain the maximum utilisation of the expensive carbon fibre. Thus the structure should be buckling stable at the highest possible strain. Because of the constraint on the global bending stiffness of the blade the stiffest material will always be oriented in the axial direction of the blade. Therefore it has been chosen to use two layers of glass fiber material on each side of the spar cap as buckling stabilisers. These two layers are also present in the original design so no extra material has been added. For production reasons the two layers are constraint to be of equal thickness. Clearly it will be cost neutral compared to the original design to vary the orientation of the glass fiber layers. This leads to the following configuration of layup for the spar cap Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Layup and design variables for the spar cap

The layup is characterised by Table 2.

Orientation	$[\theta_1, \theta_2, 0^\circ, \theta_3, \theta_4]$
Material (with epoxy resin)	[glass, glass, carbon, glass, glass],
Thickness	[0.3mm, 0.3mm, 10mm, 0.3mm, 0.3mm].

Table 2

The orientations θ_1 to θ_4 have been used as design variables in the optimization where the minimum eigenvalue (I.e. the critical buckling load) is maximized using a bound formulation. The optimizer used is the Method of Moving Asymptotes with bound formulation, developed by Svanberg (Ref . 8). In principle the optimization formulation is formulated as Eqn. 14.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Maximize} \quad \min(\lambda_k(\mathbf{x})) \quad k=1,2,\dots, n \\
 & \text{subject to} \quad g_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0 \quad i=1,2,\dots, q \\
 & \quad \quad \quad x_j^{\min} \leq x_j \leq x_j^{\max} \quad j=1,2,\dots, n
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Where $\min(\lambda_k)$ is the minimum of n eigenvalues, say the 5 first eigenvalues. $g_i(x)$ is the i 'th constraint function, which are functions of the design variables. In this example the mass of the structure is used. This constraint is not active in the present optimization since the design variables have no influence on the mass of the structure. But MMA requires at least one constraint function to be set. x_j^{\min} and x_j^{\max} are the simple constraints on the values of the design variables. Here the orientation min-max is $-\pi/2$ to $\pi/2$.

As the two glass fiber layers are thin compared to thickness of the layup their contribution to the global stiffness of the layup is not very significant, so performing the optimization should not be expected to give radical changes in the buckling load. The optimized design was found to be $[-17^\circ, 17^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ for the orientation of the plies. The improvement of 14% on the buckling load is not very significant (see Fig. 6). But it should be considered relative to the fact that the only thing, which has been changed in the design, is the orientation of the outer two layers of 0.3mm of glass fiber on each side of the layup. With this in mind it is considered to be a satisfying improvement of the performance of the structure.

Fig. 6: Iteration history for optimization of glass orientation.

Original design $[-45^\circ, 45^\circ, 0, -45^\circ, 45^\circ]$. Optimized design $[-17^\circ, 17^\circ, 0, 90^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

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